

DIACHRONIC INVESTIGATION OF TRANSPORT TERMINOLOGY REGARDING HORSE TACK AND CARRIAGES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Masharipov Jahongir Axmedovich

Urganch State University, Uzbekistan

j.masharipov.4264688@gmail.com

Annotation: The article investigates the historical background of terminology in connection with horse tack, carriages and its main components. The terms are taken from Uzbek and English languages' explanatory dictionaries. Historical background of types of carriages is illustrated as well.

Key words: term, horse, horse tack, carriage, chariot, wheel, history.

The establishment and development of every terminology system is closely connected with the creation and flourishing of a relevant domain. Furthermore, it has particular characteristics in terms of that field [1;22]. So, the creation, development and flourishing of transport terminology in Uzbek and English languages has its way of developing and genetic bases.

During ancient times, our ancestors mostly dealt with hunting and agriculture. Gradually, as time passed they had to move to explore other areas in the search of land and finding animals. This, in turn, required an assistance regarding travelling. As they had already begun taming certain animals, they also attempted to handle them so that they could ride them.

For most of human history, there was no faster way to travel over land than on a horse. When it comes to transporting people and their possessions, horses have two important advantages: They can run very fast and very far. Their speed and endurance are amazing for a creature so large, making them the ideal animals to carry people and goods around the world.

Horses offer other advantages as well. Since they eat grass, horses can go almost anywhere that humans can, eating as they go. And unlike cows and camels, which must sit and rest to digest food, a horse's digestive system allows it to graze and walk all day. By carrying people, goods, and ideas between civilizations, horses changed history [5].

Horses have been intimately involved in human history since the dawn of civilization, with signs of mankind's four-legged friends being discovered in ancient cities that are nearly six thousand years old. From plowing fields to delivering messages, and moving goods and people, horses have stayed busy throughout a variety of different occupations. However, while they appear often and in many different roles throughout history, their geographic influence was by no means ubiquitous at all times.

In some areas, such as ancient Rome, they were quite rare to find, as Romans tended to use other beasts of burden for hard labor. This meant they only needed horses specifically for things like travel, war, or the postal system. However, in places like the Eurasian steppe, where the Mongols or Huns originated from, the grass was in plenty — an important consideration for living transportation — and horses were part and parcel with life itself.

By the Middle Ages, better equipment and larger breeds led to horses finding a more important role in European society as well. Heavily armor-laden knights, in particular, are especially famous using them for transportation and battle. The use of horses has certainly ebbed and flowed over time depending on when and where one might look. But perhaps the most incredible fact about the history of horses, at least as far as transportation is concerned, is that although their **gear** improved over time, they continued to remain the top transportation option for millennia before the automobile came along and stole the show.

While horses have been around for a long time, riding horses remained a highly skillful craft until things like the **stirrup** (probably invented in the Asian steppes around the 2nd century B.C.), **saddles** (possibly originating as far back as the 3rd century B.C.), and other **tack** slowly made it much more accessible. The development of **horseshoes**, possibly by the Romans, also helped the endurance of the

horses themselves as they went about their various labors. Direct riding aside, the equine species was also instrumental in moving **carts** and **wagons** over the centuries as well. They shared these tasks to one degree or another with other draft animals like oxen and donkeys, depending on what part of the world they hailed from [6].

If we investigate Uzbek dictionary with explanations we can come across following terms regarding horse tack. Uzangi 'minish va oyoqlarni tirab o'tirish uchun xizmat qiladigan ot abzali'. Chap oyog'ini uzangiga qo'yishi bilan ot yurib ketdi. Bu ot qadimgi turkiy tilda 'yuqoriga ko'tar-' ma'nosini anglatgan üzä- fe'lining 'o'zlik' ma'nosini ifodalovchi -n qo'shimchasini olgan shaklidan —gü qo'shimchasi bilan yasalgan [7]. According to this etymology, the word 'uzangi' derived from Turkish word 'üzä' which meant 'lift'. Then to this root reflexive affix '-n' and another suffix 'gü' was added. It defined as a horse's tack which aids while getting on as well as sitting by which one can put their feet against it. A saddle in Uzbek is 'egar' which is 'Отулов (от, эшак, хачир, буғу ва бошқалар) устига уриладиган ва миниб ўтириш ҳамда юк ташиш учун мослаштирилган қулай абзал' [3;12]. Meaning: A saddle is a type of tack which is put on a transporting animals (horses, donkeys, mules, deer and others) providing convenience while riding and carrying luggage. We can notice the word 'абзал' too in that sentence in a sense of a tack [2;50]. If a horseshoe is translated directly into Uzbek language, it will be 'Ot kovushi'. However, in Uzbek there is another term for that which is 'taqa'. The etymology of the word is connected with 'join, embedding'. The translation of the definition of it according to Uzbek Dictionary is following 'horseshoe is a metal item fixed onto hoofs on animals in order to avoid mechanical harm. It was usually fixed in blacksmith's ' [4;187].

While they often shared laborious tasks, though, horses were used to pull many different transportation-focused contraptions over time, from the pharaoh's **chariot** in ancient Egypt to Queen Victoria's carriage in the 19th century. The various "Horse Eras" track their progress from a sign of status all the way through their excellence as a part of chariots, cavalry, agriculture, carriages, and finally leisure [6].

The idea of using **wheels** for transportation appears to have originated in the Eurasian Steppes of modern-day Russia and Ukraine and the world's first evidence of wheeled vehicles in mid 4th millennium BCE in the Northern Caucasus and Central Europe. Various Celtic graves searched were found to contain early **horsecarts** that hint the platforms had originally been suspended elastically. Excavations suggest that the basic construction techniques of the traditional form of wheel and **undercarriage** were initially established in Bronze Age Europe. With the successful domestication of horses almost 6,000 years ago, united with the cart provided the perfect travel solution. It is presumed most early wheels were created from wood that inevitably rots (although in some cases it can petrify and be preserved), meaning there isn't really any salvageable evidence of them. The evidence we do have available consists of impressions depicted in tombs, images on pottery and collections of ancient wheeled cart models.

The **earliest chariot** is said to have originated in Mesopotamia in about 3000 BCE. It consisted of essentially nothing more than a simple **two-wheeled basin**, carried one or two passengers, and pulled by one or two horses. They were typically lightweight and rapid, making them the favoured **warfare vehicle** of the Egyptians and the near Easterners and Europeans. The chariot was revolutionary and effective in delivering warriors to crucial areas of battle. The oldest known official chariots are said to date back to 2000 BC and were discovered in burial grounds of the Sintashta culture in modern-day Russia. The Egyptians, Hittites, Aryans, Shang Dynasty Chinese and Assyrians were among the first civilisations to make use of carriages.

According to Uzbek dictionary with explanations, carriage is in Uzbek is '**arava**' or '**aroba**' which is defined as an ancient transport means to carry luggage or human consisting of main parts such as a "**g'ildirak**" or "**tegarchik**" (**wheel**), "**o'q**" (an axe) and "**shoti**" (a shaft) [2;592]. The shafts comprised two poles each of which was approximately 4.5 meters long, two wheel hubs (In Uzbek it is '**so'loq**'), 8 steps along with "**ayg'iz**" (an upper part of a shaft). If we further analyze the terms regarding a wheel, it can be come across terms such as "**gupchak**" (the central part of wheel which

has a hole), “**to’g’in**” (the outer surface of a wheel), “**kegay**” (spoke), “**bellik**” (girth), “**aravatemir**” (carriage iron), “**aravamix**” (carriage fastener, a bolt) and “**yostiq**” (saddle pad) and others [2;592].

In 1933, a chariot burial site depicting the earliest archaeological evidence of chariots in China was discovered in Hougang and dated back to the rule of King Wu Ding of the late Shang Dynasty c. 1250 BCE. In Ancient China, chariots were typically two-wheeled vehicles drawn by two or four horses harnessed to a single draught pole. The chariot was used primarily as an attack and pursuit war vehicle. The Chinese chariots, commonly called “**gold chariots**”, “**attack chariots**”, or “**weapons chariots**”, allowed military commanders a mobile platform to control troops and provided soldiers and archers with increased mobility. The Chinese use of chariots reached its peak from the 8th to 5th centuries BCE, and although chariots appeared in more significant numbers, charioteers were very often defeated in battle.

Due to the appalling condition of British roads, carriages were not introduced in England till around 1555. Typically crafted from primarily wood and iron, carriages were vehicles consisting of a **four-wheeled wagon** with one or two **axles**, a **rounded roof** and **seats**. At first, the carriages used a **leather suspension**, but in the 17th century arrived the great innovation of **spring suspension**, which consisted of curved bars of metal on which the carriage body rode. This meant passengers could travel in comfort on the city streets, and with the eventual discovery of rubber and rubber processing, **rubber wheels** were added, making the ride even smoother.

Horse-drawn carriages in a myriad of formats vastly became the defining form of transport. Carriage horses could typically be kept in stables or, among royalty and aristocracy, in what was called “**mews**”. The mews, situated on or near the family grounds, contained **stables** for the horses and a carriage house and housing for carriage staff. The most famous, owned by the Queen, is the Royal Mews at the Buckingham Palace grounds in London, England. As the centuries passed, an array of carriages entered the mainstream[8].

Diachronic approach towards horse tack and carriages covers several distinctive and unique terms in both English and Uzbek languages. The historical background of carriages and chariots are also noteworthy.

REFERENCES:

1. Axmedov O.S. Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida soliq-bojxona terminlarining lingvistik tahlil va tarjima muammolari. Monografiya.-T.:2020.
2. O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi.-T: 2003.-A harfi.
3. O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi.-T: 2003.-E harfi.
4. O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi.-T: 2003.-Q harfi.

INTERNET SOURCES

5. <https://www.amnh.org/exhibitions/horse/how-we-shaped-horses-how-horses-shaped-us/trade-and-transportation#:~:text=When%20it%20comes%20to%20transporting,offer%20other%20advantages%20as%20well.>
6. <https://www.ofhorse.com/view-post/How-Were-Horses-Used-as-Transportation-Throughout-History#top>
7. <https://uz.wiktionary.org/wiki/uzangi>
8. <https://www.cookscarriages.com/history-of-the-horse-drawn-carriage>